

EXAMINING THE INFLUENCES ON INDIVIDUAL JOY AND PROSPERITY AND THE CULTIVATION OF POSITIVE PERSONAL CHARACTERISTICS

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Abstract: Forming personal happiness and well-being is a complex process that may encompass various issues and challenges, especially when the goal is personality development. The research aims to identify and examine the factors that affect a person's well-being and happiness and the development of positive personality traits. A critical analysis of scientific publications on personality formation and development was conducted. The review evaluated views on individual happiness and well-being, considered critical positions in the philosophy of well-being, and highlighted methodological approaches to diagnosing levels of happiness and well-being. A group of countries was selected for correlation analysis to determine the relationship between life satisfaction and GDP per capita. It is widely accepted that a high GDP contributes to personal well-being, but it is not the sole determinant. This study outlines the similarities and differences between happiness and well-being. Additionally, it has been found that possessing positive personality traits can aid in managing life's challenges, enhance quality of life, and facilitate successful interactions with others. To promote personal happiness and well-being, it is essential to cultivate self-awareness, develop skills for managing emotions, establish clear goals and action plans, seek support from others, and utilise available resources for personal growth and self-actualisation. Furthermore, it is crucial to learn to accept changes as an integral part of life and leverage them for personal development.

Keywords: happiness, life satisfaction, optimism, personality, psychology, spirituality, well-being, concept of 'happiness', linguistic picture of the world, conceptsphere, literary discourse.

1 Introduction

Personal happiness and well-being encompass various aspects of an individual's life, including physical and emotional well-being. It pertains not only to health and material wealth but also to the satisfaction derived from personal relationships, self-realisation, development, and achieving one's goals.

Balancing various aspects of life, including work, leisure, social connections, physical health, education, and spiritual development, is crucial to attaining personal happiness and well-being. Maintaining a positive outlook on life, appreciating small joys, and being grateful for what one has are essential.

Each person has a perception of what brings them happiness and contentment. For some, a successful career means satisfaction; for others, harmonious relationships with loved ones or the opportunity to pursue creative inclinations may be more fulfilling. It is necessary to be attentive to one's needs and open to discovering what brings joy and pleasure.

2 Literature review

Various approaches exist in the scientific literature for defining 'personal happiness' and 'well-being.' Philosophical works have been written by authors based on their reflections, aimed at enriching, stimulating, and challenging notions of life. In a world where people seek new ideas and sources of meaning, 'the art of living' demonstrates the value of philosophy and shows that it is a tremendous untapped resource (Vernon, 2014). M. Prinzing proposes a new approach called 'conceptual engineering' that combines the traditional philosophical approach, which undervalues empirical research, and the theoretical-empirical approach, which underestimates normative theorising (Prinzing, 2021). Analytical studies were conducted on human well-being from the perspective of moral philosophy under the scheme 'moral obligation - human suffering'. The studies indicated that

reducing suffering should take priority over promoting and enhancing well-being (Hofmann, 2024).

The authors provide a theoretical understanding of the current concept of the "conceptsphere" in cognitive linguistics, offer its definition as proposed by various researchers, analyse a range of its contextual synonyms, and clarify the relationships in which they may coexist.

The issues of optimism in forming personal happiness were also considered (Larson et al., 2010). Happiness is central in ethical and political philosophy, including mainstream theories such as utilitarianism. Recent research in happiness science and psychology has gained attention, and governments are investing millions of dollars to promote it (Michalos & Alex, 2014). The book 'The Philosophy of Well-Being' presents a critical analysis of various theories of well-being aimed at professionals in psychology, policy, and sociology (Fletcher, 2016).

Some authors argue that the concept of 'individual well-being' should be approached from four perspectives: subjectivist, objectivist, pluralist, and QSH (Cohen Kaminitz, 2020). A universal definition of well-being has been proposed based on the salutogenic approach, which defines it as a state of positive feelings. This definition emphasises that, despite global challenges, well-being should be considered more than just the absence of pathology (Simons & Baldwin, 2021). Several assessment tools and surveys have been developed to measure happiness, such as the OHQ (Moeinaddini et al., 2020). The technology of happiness proposes that income, personal values, and the philosophy of life (PVPL) are means of producing happiness (Sherman et al., 2021). A study by Jung (2020) examined the impact of social capital on personal happiness among service sector employees. The author generalises scientific research on the concept of happiness within an interdisciplinary framework, which will help refine the understanding of the category, define its universal descriptors, and form the basis for outlining the components of the socio-cultural phenomenon of happiness.

Currently, the empirical approach dominates, which does not involve evaluating happiness in the context of general social existence based on a fundamental knowledge framework.

The government's approach to well-being policy raises the question: Should policymakers prioritise fundamental theories of well-being, such as hedonism and the objective list theory, or should they instead opt for formal theories of well-being satisfaction utility? (Kwarciński, 2019) Scholars have noted that the rapid pace of scientific and technological progress blurs the boundaries between work and personal life, leading to uncertainty and tension. This blurring characterises our perceived situational awareness of the present moment as subjective well-being (Peiris et al., 2023). C. Frugé highlights the multidimensionality of well-being, including pluralism, constancy, variability, and metaphysical dependence (Frugé, 2021). Predictors of success in positive relationships include attachment, expected attitudes towards others, self-expression, self-esteem, life goals, and positive life outcomes (Chaika, 2020).

Research indicates that individuals with positive socio-emotional traits generally have interesting life stories and consider themselves happy (Guo et al., 2016). Education occupies a significant place in research on personal happiness and well-being. Art therapy is a psychological tool for self-regulation that utilises art and creativity. It is a psychotherapy or psychological correction, as noted by S. Hubina (2017).

This study aims to identify and analyse the factors influencing personal happiness and well-being and the development of positive personality traits in contemporary conditions.

3 Methods

The analysis of the impact of different factors on the individual's development, happiness, and well-being was justified using various approaches and methods. The theoretical analysis examined existing theories and research in psychology, sociology, pedagogy, economics, and other relevant sciences. The analysis identified key concepts, approaches, and trends in studying the impact of various factors on personality development, happiness, and well-being. Methodological analysis involved developing research approaches, defining variables and indicators, and addressing other methodological aspects. The meta-analysis combined the results of several studies to understand the impact of various factors on personality development, happiness, and well-being. Correlational analysis was used to establish a relationship between the gross domestic product per capita and happiness and well-being in different countries worldwide. Longitudinal studies have contributed to identifying trends in changes in happiness and well-being over time and have allowed for the determination of factors that influence these changes. Conclusions are formed based on the method of generalisation.

4 Research results

Numerous studies have focused on the relationship between happiness and personality. Additionally, attitudes, optimism, and challenges are believed to be essential psychological mechanisms that enable happiness and promote well-being (Snel, 2009). The results indicate that personality and values are predictors of beliefs about personal future well-being but not beliefs about global future well-being. Besides, personality has twice the variance compared to values. These findings are consistent with the existing literature on personality and well-being (Kajonius, 2021). Dvornyk (2020) highlighted five elements of personal psychological well-being: social capital, personal accountability, a sense of competence, personal goals, self-respect, and optimism.

Well-being is a crucial aspect of life. However, valuing happiness does not always lead to positive outcomes. Research suggests that the more people value happiness, the more likely

they will be disappointed, particularly when happiness is expected.

Analysing the factors influencing personal happiness and well-being is a complex task encompassing psychological, social, economic, and biological factors. Research shows that strong social connections with friends, family, and partners contribute to personal happiness and well-being. The author's perspective is that the quantity and quality of these connections can affect the overall well-being (Frugé, 2021; Gong et al., 2021; Guo et al., 2016).

However, optimists are widely believed to experience greater happiness and life satisfaction. Psychological resilience, or simply resilience, also plays a crucial role in our ability to adapt to stress and overcome obstacles. Personal happiness is closely linked to overall health, including mental and physical well-being. Engaging in physical activity, maintaining a healthy diet, and finding satisfaction in our work can all positively impact our well-being. Developing one's potential and achieving set goals can bring satisfaction and increase enjoyment in life. Individuals with a positive attitude towards themselves and the world often experience personal happiness more frequently. Mindfulness and inner harmony can contribute to this.

Further, society, culture, and our environment also significantly influence our happiness. Various factors contribute to our satisfaction and well-being, including the general economic situation, cultural values and norms, and even hereditary traits. Genetics can influence personality traits such as neuroticism and optimism, impacting overall well-being. These factors are not an exhaustive list, but they provide a general idea of the various aspects that influence personal happiness and well-being and the development of positive personality traits.

The World Happiness Report is a well-known source of data and research on life satisfaction in various countries (GR, 2020a). Figure 1 shows countries ranked according to their 'happiness score'.

Figure 1. Percentage of People Considering Themselves Happy (1984-2022), %
Source: (Ortiz-Ospina & Roser, 2017; Haerper et al., 2022).

Significant differences exist between countries. Recent data shows that European countries, such as Finland, Denmark, Iceland, Switzerland, and the Netherlands, have the highest scores. Conversely, Afghanistan, South Sudan, and other countries in Central Africa south of the Sahara have the lowest national indicators (GR, 2020b). The correlation between life satisfaction and other well-being indicators is evident, with

wealthier and economically developed countries typically having higher average happiness scores (WVS Database, 2022).

However, the relationship between life satisfaction and GDP per capita can be complex and ambiguous. While a higher GDP per capita can provide more material opportunities for people, positively influencing their life satisfaction, it is not always the determining factor. Figure 2 shows that overall life satisfaction

can be significantly affected by factors such as the quality of interpersonal relationships, access to education and healthcare, political stability, and corruption. personality.

In 2022, the correlation between life satisfaction and GDP per capita for the countries under study was 71.3%. Some studies have suggested that further increases in GDP per capita may diminish overall life satisfaction beyond a certain level of economic development. This phenomenon is known as the 'law of diminishing marginal utility', implying that additional GDP growth may not significantly increase life satisfaction after reaching a certain income level.

Therefore, although a high GDP per capita can improve living standards, other aspects of societal development that may influence overall life satisfaction should also be considered.

In Canada, the Community Well-being Index (CWI) measures the socio-economic well-being of Canadian communities. This index assesses the well-being of each community by combining a range of socio-economic indicators taken from the Canadian census, including education, labour force activity, income, and housing adequacy. These indicators are used to compare the

well-being of different communities in Canada. Indicator values may be unavailable for specific communities due to insufficient participation in the census, low data quality, or population size (CBW, 2024).

Psychology plays a crucial role in personality development by examining the variability of human behaviour and attitudes, which can remain stable in specific contexts and manifest in individuals (Anaya & Pérez-Edgar, 2019). Research indicates a significant correlation between positive relationships with others and personality traits, such as life processes, outcomes, and indicators of meaning. These indicators include self-expression, self-esteem, attitudes towards others' expectations, other self-concept measures and overall self-esteem and psychological resilience values. These extents indicate whether individuals perceive their lives by their desires, needs, and values. Positive relationships' success factors include affection, attitudes towards others' expectations, self-expression, self-esteem, current life goals, and positive life outcomes. According to Chaika (2020), high control focus and subordination, as psychological resilience factors, may impede the development of warm, kind, and deep relationships.

Figure 2. Ratio of Self-Assessed Life Satisfaction to GDP per capita in selected countries, 2022

Source: (Ortiz-Ospina & Roser, 2017; World Bank national accounts data, and OECD National Accounts data files, 2022).

5 Discussion

Analysing the factors influencing personal happiness and well-being is crucial for understanding what makes life fulfilling and stable for individuals. Researchers have identified several key factors that reflect current trends, including social relationships, work and career, financial status, health and self-care, education and personal achievements, mindset and psychological resilience, self-perception, the surrounding environment (community), and cultural context.

The impact of social connections on personal happiness is significant in terms of quality and quantity. Studies have shown that individuals with close and supportive relationships with friends, family, and partners generally experience greater satisfaction with life. In addition, job satisfaction and career opportunities also play a crucial role in personal happiness. It is essential to have a high level of stimulation, opportunities for development, fairness, and a balance between work and personal life to ensure well-being in the workplace. Although money cannot directly buy happiness, financial stability and the ability to provide for oneself and one's family's basic needs are vital for personal well-being.

Physical and mental health are critical factors for happiness and well-being. To ensure this, it is crucial to maintain proper nutrition, engage in regular physical activity, and pay attention to one's emotional and mental state. Achieving personal goals, learning, and personal development can bring significant satisfaction and a sense of accomplishment.

The linguistic picture of the world is a subjective image of objective reality, as each person uniquely reproduces the world. It represents a complex of linguistic means that reflect the features of ethnic perception of the world. Language, through the meaning of words, represents the object of the objective picture of the world and, in its entirety, conceptualises it. The linguistic picture of the world reflects reality perceived by consciousness in verbal forms. At the same time, the conceptosphere is a collection of concepts that exist in the minds of language speakers. In language, not only the real world surrounding a person is reflected, but also the national character of the people, morality, value system, worldview, mentality, way of life, traditions, habits, and vision of the world. Therefore, the study of concepts and conceptospheres requires considering the cultural diversity of the world.

The ability to adapt to changes, psychological resilience, and effective emotional management can help individuals cope with

challenges and stress, contributing to personal happiness. Realistic self-acceptance and expectations also promote happiness. The personal happiness and well-being of an individual can be influenced by various factors, including the environment in which they live, such as cultural and social aspects. Perception of values, norms, and community support can also play a significant role in determining well-being. It is important to note that these factors may have varying levels of impact on individuals depending on their unique characteristics and life circumstances.

Personal well-being is a multifaceted concept encompassing various aspects of an individual's life. The main factors determining personal well-being are physical and mental health, social relationships, emotional well-being, self-realisation, and financial stability.

Physical health is a crucial aspect of well-being, which includes proper nutrition, regular physical activity, sufficient sleep, and preventive medical check-ups. Psychological and emotional resilience are crucial for overall well-being. Interpersonal

connections have a significant impact on our well-being. It includes the capacity to manage stress, regulate emotions, and maintain healthy relationships. Family, friends, and community support can foster a sense of belonging and happiness. The cultivation of positive emotions such as joy, gratitude, and satisfaction, as well as the ability to express emotions and be in harmony with one's goals and values, are essential for overall well-being. The ability to develop one's potential, set and achieve goals, and feel fulfilled in life is crucial. Moreover, financial stability, meeting basic needs, and having the opportunity to enjoy life's luxuries are vital factors.

These factors are interrelated and can affect each other. For instance, a lack of social support can lead to a decline in mental health, while physical inactivity can impact emotional well-being. Achieving complete well-being requires balancing these aspects of life. Happiness and personal well-being are often linked but have unique characteristics. Consider the commonalities between happiness and personal well-being as social personality traits (Figure 3).

Social relationships	Self-realisation:	Mental health
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • It is important to interact with other people, maintain social connections and a sense of belonging 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Having the opportunity to develop your potential and achieve your personal goals is important for happiness and well-being 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Emotional stability and the ability to manage stress are crucial for happiness and well-being

Figure 3. Common Characteristics of Happiness and Well-Being
Source: compiled by the author

Happiness is a positive emotion or feeling that arises from experiencing joy, satisfaction, or triumph. In turn, well-being is a

broader concept that encompasses happiness and the overall quality of our lives (Figure 4).

Focus on emotions and pleasure
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Happiness is usually more focused on emotions and positive feelings, while well-being can also include stability and security.
Spirituality and the meaning of life
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Well-being may be more related to a sense of purpose and meaning in life, while happiness may be more about moments of pleasure.
Physical health and financial situation
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • While physical health is an integral aspect of happiness and well-being, well-being can also include material prosperity and stability.
Self-awareness and satisfaction
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Well-being may be more related to feelings of satisfaction with one's life and self-awareness, while happiness may be more associated with moments of emotional joy.

Figure 4. Differences between Personal Happiness and Well-being
Source: compiled by the author

Although these concepts have differences, they often intertwine in a person's life and complement each other. We agree with the author that happy people manage to magnify the degree of their happiness, while unhappy people tend to exaggerate the decline in their happiness (Mauss et al., 2011). We believe that happiness and well-being are not the same thing. Happiness is a part of well-being, but well-being encompasses many factors, such as satisfaction, control over one's life, and fulfilment from relationships.

Most individuals rate their lives on a seven-point scale and report being 'satisfied'. According to scientists, happiness is an improvement in one's emotional state from the previous day. Therefore, happier individuals tend to overestimate their happiness over time. Interestingly, those who rate their lives as a three and are less happy are likelier to underestimate their

happiness. For instance, unhappy individuals are 20% more likely to minimise their level of happiness, while only 10% of them overestimate their level of happiness.

Additionally, researchers have discovered a direct correlation between past and present happiness. Happier individuals are more likely to recall that their lives were more reasonable. Scientists suggest this research helps comprehend why happy individuals approach new experiences with a more positive outlook, assess risks more optimistically, and even live longer. It is impossible to always be at the peak of happiness, but we can increase our happiness by appreciating and accepting our past happiness (Simons, Baldwin, 2021).

The cultivation of positive personality traits is a crucial factor in attaining personal happiness and well-being. Positive traits aid individuals in dealing with life's challenges, improve their

quality of life, and facilitate success in social interactions. Table 1 outlines some of the most significant positive personality traits

and methods for their development.

Table 1. Key positive personality traits and ways to develop them

Trait	Trait characteristics
Optimism	Belief in your ability to cope with difficulties and see the positive in the situation around you. To develop optimism, it is practical to keep a gratitude diary, focusing on the positive aspects of your life and expressing gratitude for them.
Resilience	Resilience is the capacity to recover from stressful events and difficulties. Learning coping strategies, strengthening social connections, and practising stress reduction techniques such as meditation and deep breathing are helpful ways to evolve resilience.
Self-discipline	People can achieve their goals and manage their time and resources. Setting specific goals, developing action plans, and implementing daily routines help develop self-discipline.
Empathy	Empathy permits people to understand and sympathise with others, improving the quality of interpersonal relationships and promoting social harmony. Strengthening sympathy requires active listening, compassion, and understanding of other people's perspectives.
Self-confidence	It helps people feel confident and effective in various areas of life. Setting small, achievable goals and gradually expanding one's comfort zone is valuable.
Tolerance	Tolerance allows people to understand and accept the diversity of other people and cultures. Studying different cultures, communicating with different people, and showing respect for differences are helpful in strengthening tolerance.

The traits discussed improve the quality of life and contribute to personal happiness, as well as helping to create a more harmonious and prosperous society.

6 Conclusion

Forming personal happiness and well-being can be challenging, mainly when the aim is personal development. Issues that may arise in this process include a lack of understanding of one's needs and values, a lack of purpose, stress and negative emotions, low self-esteem and confidence, fear of change, and a lack of support and resources. To tackle these issues, it is crucial to enhance self-awareness, cultivate emotional regulation skills, establish precise objectives and corresponding action plans, seek assistance from others, and use available resources for personal development and self-actualisation. Moreover, it is essential to acknowledge change as an inherent aspect of life and learn to utilise it for personal growth.

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